

THE ESSENCE OF THE CONCEPT OF DEVELOPMENT OF PROMOTION QUALITIES IN TEACHERS OF PRIMARY EDUCATION.

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Abstract: The content of this article is aimed at revealing the essence of the development of organizational and advocacy qualities in primary education teachers. Scientifically based opinions are also presented about the need to develop the characteristics of personal creativity in primary education teachers.

Key words: primary education, teacher, organization, qualities of promotion, characteristics of personal creativity, scientific considerations.

Introduction.

The development of education in the conditions of social changes and modernization of the educational system while preserving and glorifying values that have been preserved for centuries requires the training of teachers who are able to organize activities. This requirement, reflected in the state educational standards, is compatible with the issue of "organization of scheduled and extracurricular activities of primary school students", one of the objects of professional activity of graduates.

In recent years, in our republic, on the basis of national values, the heritage of enlightened figures, the normative foundations for improving education, educating the young generation in the spirit of patriotism, forming feelings of national pride, and developing professional and social training of future specialists have been created. "Using the ideas of modern enlighteners in the education of the young generation" and carrying out innovative researches are defined as leading directions. This will expand the pedagogical possibilities of teaching the

pedagogical heritage of representatives of the Jadidist movement to students of higher educational institutions.

Research methodology: comparative study of scientific-methodical literature, systematic analysis, pedagogical diagnosis, interview, scientific forecasting, modeling, monitoring, pedagogical experiment-testing, theoretical, empirical and practical methods are used in the article.

Analysis and results.

O.A.Abdullina developed the content and types of pedagogical skills in accordance with the development of a functional approach in her work, specific types of work of a teacher-educator. He distinguished the following pedagogical functions:

organization of the educational process and management of learning activities of learners;

conducting educational work with students outside the classroom and managing their self-education;

“carrying out political and educational activities among the population and promoting pedagogical knowledge”;

study and transfer of advanced pedagogical experience, analysis and generalization of advanced pedagogical experience, and generalization of personal experience; independent education.

A.P. Voychenko said that the professional preparation of a graduate of a pedagogical university for pedagogical work is an integrated education, the components of which are interrelated, and the absence of at least one of them leads to an imbalance in the personality of a future teacher.

T.Z. Munavarova reveals this concept in the context of the relationship between theoretical and practical preparation of future teachers for pedagogical activity. According to the level of professional-pedagogical training: high, medium and low, he divides the groups of students in the dissertation work.

Conclusions

Analysis of the theory and practice of training students of higher educational institutions of pedagogy for future professional activity leads to understanding of the special relevance and importance of the problem of forming the professional skills of future primary school teachers in a rapidly changing world.

The developed theoretical rules and experimental data allow us to draw the following conclusions:

Extensive analysis of literary sources, official materials and documents in various fields of modern science, as well as the analysis of studies devoted to solving the problem of preparing future teachers for professional pedagogical activities allowed us to come to this conclusion. The result of these works is the formation of their professional skills.

List of used literature.

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